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Rohingya Crisis in Bangladesh and How to Solve It

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Abstract

The Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh, triggered by the mass exodus of Rohingya refugees from Myanmar due to violence and persecution, presents significant humanitarian and socio-political challenges. Bangladesh has provided shelter to over a million refugees, primarily in Cox's Bazar, creating immense pressure on its resources and infrastructure. This paper examines the root causes of the Rohingya crisis, focusing on the historical and ethnic tensions in Myanmar, and explores the impacts on Bangladesh, including economic strain, social instability, and environmental degradation. Potential solutions are analyzed, including international diplomatic pressure on Myanmar, repatriation efforts under safe conditions, and regional cooperation for long-term refugee support. It also highlights the need for global partnerships, improved resource allocation, and the importance of addressing human rights violations. The study underscores that sustainable solutions require coordinated action, addressing both the immediate humanitarian needs and the underlying causes of the crisis.

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Rohingya Crisis in Bangladesh and How to Solve It

1.1 Introduction

The Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh refers to the ongoing humanitarian and refugee crisis caused by the mass exodus of Rohingya Muslims from Myanmar (formerly known as Burma) to Bangladesh. The crisis has its roots in decades of persecution, discrimination, and violence against the Rohingya ethnic minority in Myanmar, which is predominantly a Buddhist-majority country.¹

The crisis escalated significantly in August 2017 when the Myanmar military launched a brutal crackdown in Rakhine State, a predominantly Rohingya-populated region. This military operation included widespread killings, sexual violence, and the burning of Rohingya villages, leading to the displacement of hundreds of thousands of Rohingya people. These actions were widely condemned by the international community and were described as ethnic cleansing by many.²

As a result of the violence, over a million Rohingya refugees fled to neighboring Bangladesh, primarily seeking shelter in Cox's Bazar, a district in southeastern Bangladesh. The rapid influx of refugees placed immense strain on Bangladesh's infrastructure, resources, and economy. The Rohingya refugees often live in overcrowded and inadequate conditions in sprawling refugee camps, making them vulnerable to disease, food shortages, and other hardships.³

The Bangladesh government, international organizations, and humanitarian agencies have been providing aid and support to the Rohingya refugees. However, the situation remains complex and challenging, with ongoing concerns about the refugees' long-term prospects, their rights, and the need for a sustainable solution to the crisis. Efforts to repatriate Rohingya refugees to Myanmar have been slow and faced numerous obstacles, including concerns about their safety and citizenship rights in Myanmar.

The Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh has drawn significant international attention and has raised questions about human rights violations, the responsibility of the international community, and the need for a comprehensive resolution to address the root causes of the conflict in Myanmar. It remains a critical and ongoing issue in the region and on the global stage.

1.2 The Root Causes of Rohingya Crisis

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rohingya_people# . Visited on 11th June 2024

² <https://www.unicef.org/emergencies/rohingya-crisis> Visited on 15th June 2024

³ <https://news.un.org/en/story/2023/08/1139977> Visited on 16th June 2024

The Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh has deep historical and socio-political roots. Several key factors have contributed to the crisis, including:

1. **Discrimination and Persecution in Myanmar**⁴: The Rohingya, an ethnic Muslim minority group, have faced decades of discrimination, persecution, and violence in Myanmar. The government of Myanmar has denied them citizenship and many basic rights, rendering them stateless and marginalized. This discrimination has been enshrined in Myanmar's legal and political systems.

2. **Ethnic and Religious Tensions**: The Rohingya crisis is closely linked to ethnic and religious tensions in Myanmar. The Rohingya are predominantly Muslim in a country where the majority of the population is Buddhist. This has fueled a sense of otherness and led to conflict.⁵

3. **Military Crackdowns**: The crisis escalated in August 2017 when the Myanmar military launched a brutal crackdown in Rakhine State, home to a significant Rohingya population. This military operation included widespread human rights abuses, such as extrajudicial killings, sexual violence, and the burning of Rohingya villages.⁶

4. **Push Factors**: The violence and persecution in Myanmar have acted as "push factors," forcing hundreds of thousands of Rohingya to flee their homes in search of safety and security. Many crossed the border into Bangladesh.

5. **Mass Migration to Bangladesh**: The influx of Rohingya refugees into Bangladesh, particularly in the Cox's Bazar district, has placed immense strain on the resources and infrastructure of the host country. The sheer scale of the migration has made it challenging for Bangladesh to provide adequate assistance and services to the refugees.

6. **Humanitarian Crisis**: The refugee camps in Bangladesh are overcrowded and face numerous challenges, including limited access to food, clean water, healthcare, and education. The conditions in these camps have given rise to a humanitarian crisis.⁷

7. **Lack of Citizenship Rights**: The Rohingya issue is compounded by the fact that Myanmar does not recognize the Rohingya as citizens, effectively rendering them stateless. This lack of citizenship rights has made it difficult for the international community to intervene effectively.⁸

8. **Political Complexity**: The Rohingya crisis is further complicated by the complex political dynamics in Myanmar, including the military's influence in the country's politics. Efforts to resolve the crisis have been hampered by these complexities.

9. **International Response**: The international community has condemned the actions of the Myanmar military and provided humanitarian aid to the Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh. However, there have been challenges in achieving a lasting political solution and ensuring the safe repatriation of refugees to Myanmar.

⁴ <https://minorityrights.org/communities/muslims-and-rohingya> Visited on 16th June 2024

⁵ <https://unric.org/en/myanmar-the-rohingya-crisis> Visited on 17th June 2024

⁶ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-41566561#:> Visited on 19th June 2024

⁷ <https://unric.org/en/myanmar-the-rohingya-crisis/> Visited on 19th June 2024

⁸ <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2022/8/25/rohingya-exodus-explained-in-maps-and-charts/> Visited on 20th June 2024.

The Rohingya crisis is a multifaceted issue with deep-seated historical and political factors. It remains a significant challenge for Myanmar, Bangladesh, and the broader international community, as efforts to address the root causes and find a sustainable solution continue.

1.3 History of Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh

The Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh has its roots in a long history of discrimination, persecution, and violence against the Rohingya ethnic minority in Myanmar. Here is a brief overview of the historical context leading up to the crisis:

1. **Pre-Independence Period:** The Rohingya have lived in the region of Rakhine State in Myanmar (formerly known as Burma) for centuries. However, their status has been a contentious issue, even before Myanmar's independence from British colonial rule in 1948. The post-independence government began to enact policies that marginalized and discriminated against the Rohingya.⁹

2. **1982 Citizenship Law:** In 1982, the Myanmar government passed the Burmese nationality law, which effectively denied the Rohingya citizenship. This law left many Rohingya stateless, without access to basic rights and services.¹⁰

3. **Intercommunal Violence:** Over the years, there have been periodic outbreaks of violence and discrimination against the Rohingya by both the government and ethnic Rakhine Buddhists. These incidents included attacks, restrictions on movement, and displacement.

4. **2012 Domestic Violence:** In 2012, a wave of violence erupted in Rakhine State, leading to the displacement of tens of thousands of Rohingya. Many were forced to live in squalid camps or flee across the border into Bangladesh.¹¹

5. **2017 Military Crackdown:** The crisis escalated significantly in August 2017 when the Myanmar military launched a brutal crackdown in response to attacks on police posts by an insurgent group, the Arakan Rohingya Salvation Army (ARSA). This military operation included widespread human rights abuses, such as extrajudicial killings, sexual violence, and the burning of Rohingya villages, which resulted in the mass displacement of hundreds of thousands of Rohingya.¹²

6. **Influx into Bangladesh:** The violence in Rakhine State forced hundreds of thousands of Rohingya to flee Myanmar and seek refuge in Bangladesh. This sudden and massive influx of

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https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340754874_Rohingya_The_History_of_a_Muslim_Identity_in_Myanmar_Summary_and_Keywords Visited on 25th June 2024

¹⁰ <https://pulitzercenter.org/stories/between-burma-and-bangladesh-rohingya-stateless-people>, Visited on 29th June 2024

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2012_Rakhine_State_riots Visited on 1 July

¹² ¹² <https://www.unicef.org/emergencies/rohingya-crisis> Visited on 15th June 2024

refugees into Cox's Bazar, a district in southeastern Bangladesh, overwhelmed the local infrastructure and resources.

The historical context of the Rohingya crisis is characterized by discrimination, statelessness, and periodic outbreaks of violence against the Rohingya people. The crisis has led to a massive refugee population in Bangladesh and has raised significant international concerns about human rights violations and the need for a comprehensive solution that addresses the root causes of the conflict in Myanmar.

1.4 Present scenario of Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh

1. **Refugee Camps:** Hundreds of thousands of Rohingya refugees were living in overcrowded and makeshift camps in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. These camps faced significant challenges related to sanitation, healthcare, and access to education.

2. **Humanitarian Aid:** Various international organizations, including the United Nations and non-governmental organizations, were providing humanitarian assistance to the refugees. Efforts were ongoing to provide food, clean water, healthcare, and shelter to the displaced Rohingya population.

3. **Repatriation Attempts:** Despite several attempts, repatriation efforts to return Rohingya refugees to Myanmar had made little progress due to ongoing security concerns and a lack of guarantees for their safety and citizenship rights.

4. **Economic Impact on Bangladesh:** The presence of such a large refugee population placed a significant economic strain on Bangladesh. The local community in Cox's Bazar also faced challenges related to the refugee influx.

5. **International Concerns:** The Rohingya crisis remained a matter of global concern, with many nations and international organizations urging Myanmar to address the root causes of the conflict and ensure the safe return and rights of the Rohingya population.

1.5 The steps and measures taken by the Bangladesh government for Rohingya crisis

The government of Bangladesh has taken several steps in response to the Rohingya crisis to address the humanitarian needs of the refugees and manage the situation, here are some of the steps and measures taken by the Bangladesh government:

1. **Temporary Shelter:** The government of Bangladesh, in cooperation with international organizations, established refugee camps in the Cox's Bazar district to provide temporary shelter for Rohingya refugees. These camps have provided protection, food, and basic services to the displaced Rohingya population.¹³
2. **Humanitarian Assistance:** Bangladesh has worked closely with international humanitarian agencies to provide essential services, including food, clean water, healthcare, and education, to the Rohingya refugees in the camps. The government has facilitated the distribution of aid and the provision of medical care.
3. **Security:** The Bangladesh government has deployed security forces to maintain law and order in and around the refugee camps, ensuring the safety of both refugees and the host community.
4. **Vaccination Campaigns:** Bangladesh has conducted vaccination campaigns, including COVID-19 vaccinations, within the Rohingya refugee camps to protect against the spread of disease.
5. **Registration and Documentation:** The government initiated a biometric registration process for Rohingya refugees to provide them with identification cards. This helps in documenting and tracking the refugee population.
6. **Repatriation Negotiations:** Bangladesh has engaged in diplomatic efforts to negotiate with Myanmar and international organizations to facilitate the safe and voluntary return of Rohingya refugees to their homeland. However, repatriation efforts have faced challenges due to concerns about the safety and rights of the returnees.
7. **Education Initiatives:** The government has worked with international organizations to establish temporary learning centers within the refugee camps, providing educational opportunities to Rohingya children.
8. **Infrastructure Development:** Bangladesh has invested in infrastructure development in the Cox's Bazar region to support both the refugee population and the host community.
9. **International Cooperation:** The government has engaged with international partners and organizations to seek support for the Rohingya crisis, both in terms of humanitarian aid and efforts to find a lasting solution to the conflict.

Multiple international organizations, including the United Nations (UN) and various humanitarian agencies, have been actively involved in addressing the Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh. Their efforts have primarily focused on providing humanitarian assistance, advocating for the rights of Rohingya refugees, and supporting host communities. Here are some of the steps and measures taken by these organizations:

¹³ <https://reliefweb.int/report/bangladesh/rohingya-refugee-response-bangladesh-shelter-and-settlement-planning-factsheet-31-december-2022>

1.6 The steps and measures taken by the UN and Different Organization for Rohingya crisis

1. **Provision of Humanitarian Aid:** International organizations, such as the UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR), the World Food Programme (WFP), and various non-governmental organizations (NGOs), have been providing food, clean water, shelter, and healthcare services to the Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh.

2. **Healthcare Services:** Organizations like Médecins Sans Frontières (Doctors Without Borders) and the World Health Organization (WHO) have been involved in providing healthcare services, including medical treatment, vaccination campaigns, and mental health support to the refugees.

3. **Education Initiatives:** UNICEF and other organizations have established learning centers and schools within the refugee camps to provide education and psychosocial support to Rohingya children.

4. **Protection of Rights:** International organizations and human rights groups have been advocating for the protection of the rights of Rohingya refugees, including their right to citizenship, freedom of movement, and protection from violence and discrimination.

5. **Advocacy and Diplomacy:** The UN, along with diplomatic efforts from various countries and organizations, has been working to press Myanmar to address the root causes of the crisis and create conditions conducive to the safe and voluntary return of Rohingya refugees.

6. **Documentation and Registration:** The UNHCR, in collaboration with the Bangladeshi government, has been involved in registering and documenting Rohingya refugees to provide them with identification cards.

7. **Coordination and Partnerships:** International organizations have coordinated their efforts with the Bangladeshi government and local partners to ensure an effective response to the crisis. They have also sought to mobilize funding and resources to support humanitarian efforts.

8. **Support for Host Communities:** International organizations have recognized the strain on host communities in the Cox's Bazar area and have implemented projects to support these communities, including infrastructure development and economic initiatives.

9. **Advocacy for Accountability:** Various organizations have been advocating for accountability for human rights abuses and violence committed against the Rohingya in Myanmar, including calls for investigations and legal actions against those responsible.

10. **Preparation for Natural Disasters:** Given the vulnerability of the Rohingya refugee camps to natural disasters like cyclones and monsoon rains, organizations have undertaken efforts to improve camp infrastructure and enhance disaster preparedness.

These are just a few examples of the many measures taken by the United Nations, humanitarian agencies, and NGOs to address the Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh. Their work is crucial in providing aid and advocating for the rights and well-being of the Rohingya population while also seeking a lasting solution to the crisis.

Ending the Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh is a complex and multifaceted challenge, but there are several key steps and strategies that could contribute to a resolution. These steps involve a combination of diplomatic, humanitarian, and long-term solutions. Here are some ways to work towards ending the crisis.

1.7 How to put an end to Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh

1. Peaceful Resolution and Negotiation:

- Encourage dialogue and negotiations between Myanmar and Rohingya leaders to address the root causes of the crisis.
- International actors, including the United Nations and neighboring countries, should play a facilitating role in bringing the parties to the table.

2. Ensure Safe and Voluntary Repatriation:

- Create conditions in Myanmar that allow Rohingya refugees to return voluntarily and safely. This includes addressing their citizenship rights, safety, and ensuring their protection from persecution.
- Establish a monitoring mechanism to oversee the repatriation process and ensure that it is carried out transparently and with the consent of the refugees.

3. International Pressure on Myanmar:

- Maintain international pressure on Myanmar to respect human rights, grant citizenship to the Rohingya, and hold accountable those responsible for past atrocities.
- Implement targeted sanctions and restrictions, if necessary, to incentivize Myanmar to change its policies.

4. Humanitarian Assistance and Development:

- Continue to provide humanitarian aid to Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh and support the host communities.
- Invest in long-term development programs in Rakhine State, Myanmar, to address issues such as infrastructure, education, and economic development.

5. Rule of Law and Justice:

- Support international efforts to seek justice for human rights abuses and potential crimes against humanity committed against the Rohingya, including possible referrals to the International Criminal Court (ICC).

6. Global Solidarity:

- Encourage the international community to show solidarity with Bangladesh, which has borne a significant burden in hosting the Rohingya refugees.
- Mobilize funding and resources for humanitarian efforts and long-term solutions.

7. Public Awareness and Advocacy:

- Raise global awareness about the crisis and advocate for the rights of the Rohingya people.
- Engage in public diplomacy and media campaigns to keep the issue in the spotlight.

8. Conflict Prevention and Resolution:

- Work towards addressing ethnic and religious tensions in Myanmar through reconciliation efforts and reforms that promote inclusivity and social cohesion.

9. Strengthen Regional Cooperation:

- Engage with neighboring countries, such as China, India, and ASEAN nations, to seek their support and involvement in resolving the crisis.

10. Monitor and Report Human Rights Abuses:

- International organizations and human rights groups should continue to monitor the situation, document human rights abuses, and report on developments to maintain accountability.

Ending the Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh requires a sustained and coordinated effort from the international community, including governments, organizations, and civil society. It is a complex and deeply rooted issue, but a combination of diplomatic pressure, humanitarian support, and long-term solutions is crucial to making progress toward a resolution.

1.8 Conclusion

The Rohingya crisis in Bangladesh stems from the persecution of the Rohingya ethnic minority in Myanmar. It escalated significantly in August 2017 when the Myanmar military launched a brutal crackdown, leading to the mass exodus of over a million Rohingya refugees into Bangladesh. These refugees have been living in overcrowded and inadequate conditions in Cox's Bazar, with limited access to food, clean water, and healthcare. The crisis is marked by the denial of citizenship and basic rights to the Rohingya, who are predominantly Muslim in a Buddhist-majority Myanmar. Ongoing ethnic and religious tensions have resulted in violence, discrimination, and a longstanding stateless status for the Rohingya. International organizations and governments have provided humanitarian aid, and diplomatic efforts have sought to facilitate the safe repatriation of refugees to Myanmar. However, repatriation efforts have been slow, and the crisis remains complex, with ongoing concerns about human rights violations and the need for a comprehensive resolution to address the root causes of the conflict in Myanmar.